

ADAPTATION OF INFORMATION INTERACTION "USER-SYSTEM" AS A WAY TO INCREASE THE RESILIENCE OF AUTOMATED CONTROL SYSTEMS

Modern automated control systems (ACS) are human-machine systems with a complex structure, focused on performing a wide range of functions. This determines certain features of working with information in such systems, its storage and processing. Due to the significant amount of information with which operators of automated systems must interact in the process of work, often in conditions of limited time for decision-making, information overload of operators occurs, which negatively affects the quality of their work and the resilience of the ACS [1]. To solve the problem of reducing the efficiency of information interaction of the user with the system, the possibility of creating a model of the information interaction process, algorithmization and implementation of the process of adapting the characteristics of information flows coming from the system to the operator to the individual characteristics of the operator and the workflow is considered.

A number of models are proposed [2-4] to algorithmize and implement the process of adapting the user's information interaction with the system. The adaptation process is implemented as management of interconnected parameters of entity models participating in the process of information interaction.

Information flow I from the system can be described as a set of parameters:

$$I = \langle T, F, C, D \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where T is the rate of information delivery, F is the data presentation format, C is the complexity of the information, its connection with other data blocks, D is the data being transmitted.

The pace of information presentation in the ACS can be controlled in non-critical situations by changing the intensity of information presentation to the user depending on the permissible level of information load. The desired pace for the user is determined by his ability to quickly respond to data from the system, as well as the current level of fatigue and concentration. The format of information presentation can be text, graphic, tabular, audio, combined. In general, the format of data presentation is determined by a set of user interface output elements, but provided that this set can be changed in accordance with the needs and requirements of the user, the presentation format can also be adapted to the features of the user's perception of information (his cognitive portrait). Information complexity is a complex characteristic that takes into account the connections between data blocks in the subject area model, the number of connections and blocks involved in a given episode of data presentation, as well as their overlap with the user's knowledge model. Parameter D – a fragment of information transmitted to the user in a given episode of the workflow. This fragment may correspond to one block of data in the subject area, or may represent a set of blocks or part of a separate block, depending on the scenario of user interaction with the system.

The user interface in automated systems is considered as a collection of output elements, $UI = \langle E_i \rangle, i = \overline{1, n}$, each output element

$$E_i = \langle \langle x, y \rangle_i^j, T_i, c_i \rangle, j = \overline{1, m} \quad (2)$$

where $\langle x, y \rangle_i^j$ – coordinates of the vertex of the boundary of the output element in the user interface window, T_i – type of output element, c_i – criticality of the i -th output element for user work.

The set of values of the parameter T_i in model (2) coincides with the set of values of the parameter F model (1), and it is the type of output elements available in the user interface window that determines the desired data format when forming the information flow.

The criticality of an output element is determined by the specifics of the workflow. Critical elements include elements whose loss of information leads to disruption of the workflow or the inability of the user to correctly process information from the system.

Controlling the placement of output elements and their type allows you to create a personalized user interface to adapt the user's information interaction with the ACS. Critical output elements must be present in the working interface window, regardless of its adaptation.

Personalization of the user interface and management of information flow parameters allow you to configure the process of information interaction in the system, taking into account the individual characteristics of the user and the features of the workflow (work scenario in the system, subject area, etc.), reduce the risk of information overload for the ACS operator, which has a positive effect on the resilience of the system.

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